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Project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan |

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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

List of project participants

Participant organisation name	Country
Polytechnic Institute of Setúbal (IPS)	PT
St. Pölten University of Applied Sciences (STPUAS)	AT
Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences (MATE)	HU
Politehnica University of Timisoara (UPT)	RO
University Colleges Leuven Limburg (UCLL)	BE
Vidzeme University of Applied Sciences (ViA)	LV

Abbreviated terms

CDE – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

E³UDRES² – Engaged and Entrepreneurial European University as Driver for European Smart and Sustainable Regions

EEA – European Education Area

ERA – European Research Area

EU – European Union

EURASHE – European Association of Institutions in High Education

EUA – European University Association

FOREU2 – Fora of the second call of the European University Alliances

GnA – General Assembly

HEIs – Higher education institutions

KoM – Kick-off Meeting

PO – Project Officer

REA – European Research Executive Agency

WP – Work Package

Executive Summary

The E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project aims to co-create a more specific joint research and innovation strategy and a common agenda to accelerate the transformation of E³UDRES² into a European multi-institutional Research and Innovation Hub for Smart and Sustainable Regions.

This deliverable presents the D1.2 - Project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan, which will detail the strategy presented in section 2.2 of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators “Proposal template Part B: technical description”, with a clear definition and alignment between the target audiences, the communication areas and dimensions, its objectives, messages, channels, types of activities and frequency over the 36 months of the project.

The development, application and control of the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan is the responsibility of “WP1 - Project management and dissemination”. This WP ensures the project management and a widespread dissemination that considers the variety of different stakeholders and target groups of the project. The Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan, aims to achieve, above all, three of the objectives set out in Grant Agreement for this WP:

- Ensure efficient overall coordination in accordance with the defined Project Plan;
- Ensure widespread dissemination of project results to various stakeholders and communities on regional, national, European and international level;
- Promote European visibility of E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators ideas, activities, output, outcome, and impact.

Throughout this plan we will identify channels, targets, objectives, timing, and control measures for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) activities.

1. E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators visual identity

Logo and Brand Book

The visual identity is the starting point of the brand’s communication. It brings together our core values and aims to communicate the objectives and mission of the project, it’s “personality”. The logo was designed to graphically convey the values of the brand/project: the symbol of the project is the representation of the letter “e” in a humanized way (Figure 1). A happy “e” referring to the satisfaction / realization / discovery of something, reminding of a lighted lamp (idea).

Figure 1 - E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators symbol

Figure 2 - E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators symbol invert versions

Figure 3 - E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators symbol – black version

The visual expression of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project consists of its corporate visual identity, which includes the definition of a logo, typography and colours, presented in the project’s Brand Book. The brand consists of a symbol, a logotype (the project name in its own typography) and a tagline (entrepreneurs + researchers + educators + innovators). To ensure proper reading throughout the various formats, the brand features a main version and an alternative version, for maximum versatility (Figure 4 and Figure 5). The Brand book also includes an inverted colour version of the logo (in white, on a coloured background), as well as a single colour version, making it possible to use the brand in any context.

Figure 4 - E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators main logo

Figure 5 - Alternative logo (for horizontal layouts)

The main colours in the logo (blue, orange, yellow and green) will be the chromatic basis of all the project’s communication material. To enrich the graphic communication, complementary colours were also defined

(Purple, Light Blue, Gray and Black). The font used in the logo's construction is 'Now'. For internal documents, such as Word and/or PowerPoint, or in situations where it is not possible to use the predefined font, the "Arial" font family must be used.

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators is a Project financed by the European Union, so, according to the Grant Agreement, the communication must have the appropriate EU representation. For this reason, all CDE visual activities and presence will recognize EU support by displaying the European flag (emblem) and the funding statement, as defined in the Proposal.

Since the two logos appear simultaneously on the various communication pieces associated with the Project, the rules mentioned in Brand Book ensure consistency in the representation of both logos (Figure 6).

Figure 6 - E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators logo + European Union logo

Templates

All E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators CDE actions and activities must increase the visibility of the project's identity. With that in mind, graphic templates were developed for project presentations (Figure 8), background for online meetings, templates for minutes (Figure 7), meeting agendas, deliverables, press releases, newsletters, and social media accounts. The existence of the Brand Book and the creation of templates also aims to ensure the uniform and coherent use of the project's visual identity.

Figure 7 - Word templates

Figure 8 - PowerPoint template

The disclaimer “**Project No 101071317** Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency [REA]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them” was included in all the templates.

The visual identity documents (logo files, brand manual and templates) are accessible to the team members through the EMDESK shared platform. All brand files will also be made available on the project website, to ensure correct and high-quality use of the brand by external audiences.

2. Communication areas and dimensions

2.1 Communication areas

This Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan considers a comprehensive approach to communication, subdividing and detailing it into three different intervention areas: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation. The action and activities of these three areas are complementary and will take place during the 36 months of the project:

- Communication focuses on promoting the action and its results;
- Dissemination is specifically dedicated to making project results public;
- Exploitation seeks to make concrete use of the results.

Figure 9 - Communication areas

The different purposes, objectives, targets and channels of these three areas will be address in more detail later in this plan.

2.2 Target dimensions

Figure 10 - Target dimensions

In order to make planning clearer and more focused, in addition to the three areas of communication previous mentioned, in this plan we also took into account the division of project targets into two major dimensions, identified in Figure 10:

- 1st Dimension refers to the internal communication of the project itself, that is, between team members, WPs, and executive board members. The internal communication considers all the elements needed for the project to work and has also a management and organizational perspective.
- 2nd Dimension refers to the external communication. This dimension is addressed to members outside the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project team, and includes targets within the community of each consortium beneficiary institution, for which there is a capacity for more direct influence (such as researchers, managers and research centers, learners, teachers, and staff) and, in a broader approach, targets outside the consortium institutions (such as other researchers, managers and research centers, HEIs, science policy makers, EU representatives and project officer, press/media, regional stakeholders, and citizens).

Communication outside the consortium community has a more heterogeneous aspect, because there are different Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation objectives for different targets. Communication with the PO, the EU or with the science policy makers, for example, have different purposes and natures from Communication target to the press/media or citizens.

3. Channels

3.1 E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators Channels

To achieve its goals, taking into account the variety and specificity of all the targets, the CDE activities of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project will use a diverse set of Communication channels, that brings together online and offline tools.

EMDESK

The management of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project uses an online project management tool, called EMDESK (<https://www.emdesk.com/>). This is the project organization and management's main tool. This tool allows the control, monitoring and management of most of the issues related to the project in a centralized and shared way, enabling the management of deliverables and tasks, expenses, communications and document sharing, for instance. All project members have access to the EMDESK as users or as guests.

ID	Lead Participant	Start (...)	End (m...)	Actual Start	Actual End	Budget (€)	Expense (€)	Actual (P1#)	Status	Completion	Costs Consumpt...
1	IP_ IPS	M01	M36	01.10.22 (M01)	30.09.25 (M36)	€ 312,401.67	€ 22,213.72	€ 145.95	In progress (47%)	15%	7.1%
3	GI_ IPS	M01	M36	01.10.22 (M01)	30.09.25 (M36)	0.00	8,793.75	0.00	In progress	10%	-
5	MI_ IPS	M01	M36	01.10.22 (M01)	30.09.25 (M36)	0.00	0.00	0.00	In progress	10%	-
6	OI_ IPS	M01	M36	01.10.22 (M01)	30.09.25 (M36)	0.00	0.00	0.00	In progress	25%	-
7	PI_ IPS	M01	M36	01.10.22 (M01)	30.09.25 (M36)	0.00	6,457.50	0.00	In progress	30%	-
8	QI_ IPS	M12	M30	-	-	0.00	0.00	0.00	-	0%	-
9	RI_ IPS	-	M02	-	30.11.22 (M02)	0.00	0.00	0.00	Completed	100%	-
74	SI_ IPS	-	M02	-	30.11.22 (M02)	0.00	0.00	0.00	In progress	90%	-
85 elements		M01	M36	01.10.22 (M01)	-	€ 1,898,384.91	€ 30,849.14	€ 337.00		15%	1.63%

Figure 11 - EMDESK "workplan page"

The information about the entrenovators project was uploaded to the platform in month 1 - the entrenovators workplan, participants, resources, and files are available there (Figure 11). To facilitate different possibilities of members organization and information sharing, participants were assigned to different groups simultaneously (such as the IPS Management Team, the Institutions teams and WPs teams).

Complementary to EMDESK, in order to work effectively, different WPs can make use of different online collaboration tools, such as GoogleDocs, Google Drive, SharePoint, MindMeister, MS Teams, Dropbox and/or others. Those tools will be used whenever necessary to facilitate the quick exchange of ideas and suggestions by a collaborative work on the same document. The final version of the document will be always discussed in an online or face-to-face meeting between the members of the WP teams and will be stored on EMDESK.

Meetings

The project uses MS Teams for the online meetings. The meetings are the preferred tool for organizing work and ideas between team members. Each WP holds a minimum of one monthly meeting, organized by the respective leader. WP1 also holds a monthly online meeting, bringing together the leaders of all working groups. The purpose of this meeting is to correct deviations, as well as to identify and resolve risks and setbacks in the work of each team.

Every 6 months General Assembly and Executive board meeting take place on site, bringing together members of the executive board and at least one representative of each WP of each institution.

Occasionally, there may be a need to meet with other audiences outside the project team to share ideas, challenges, and results.

Meeting agendas/minutes

All meeting agendas and the respective minutes are shared with the project team members via email. These documents are also archived at EMDESK. Sharing these files allows every team member to be aware of the progress of work, anticipate potential overlaps or synergies between work groups and propose solutions.

Email

Email will be used within the project team, and also in the management and sharing of information with the PO and other stakeholders of interest to the project. This channel is used to set up meetings, send invitations, share meeting agendas, minutes, share information, and organize work.

For the internal communication of the project, EMDESK is also used to send emails to the project team members. Each group set up on EMDESK has an email account. All the emails sent by EMDESK are also sent to the institutional email of each team member.

Newsletter

The project will have a digital newsletter (Figure 12), shared through the website every six months, with the possibility of intermediate editions whenever there is relevant content that justifies it. The information about the publication of a new newsletter will be shared to the public of each institution through email distribution list or through other channels available in each beneficiary institution. This channel goal is to

raise awareness to the project existence and goals, share information about the project, events, activities, facts, and achievements.

The writing process for each issue of the newsletter will be led by the IPS-WP1, which asks the leaders of each WP to submit relevant information about the WP's activity. The information will be further selected and prepared by WP1-IPS and sent to the WP Leader for validation before the final publication.

Figure 12 - E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators newsletter graphic project

Sensitive Deliverables

The sensitive deliverables will be shared with all the project team members through EMDESK. In addition to the WP responsible for the deliverable, and of the appointed reviewer, in the preparation phase of deliverable all teams will have access to the document and are invited to contribute, leading to an increased sense of common purpose.

Public deliverables

All of the non sensitive deliverables will be made public through the project website. Sharing these documents within reach of the institutions' internal public, stakeholders, and civil society, enables to reach wider audiences, making public information about the results already achieved.

Website

The project's website is aimed to internal and external audiences and pretends to make the project, its objectives and results known. The site will be online predictably at the end of month 5.

Graphically, as visible in Figure 13 will respect the graphic identity of the project, using its colours, typography, logo and complementary graphics.

As for its structures, the website will include the following pages:

- "About Ent-r-e-novators" – description of the project, its goals and team
- "What we do" – presentation of the working groups (WP), their objectives and tasks
- "E³UDRES² Alliance" – brief presentation of the E³UDRES² Alliance

- “News & Events” – highlights, activity schedule, and press releases archive. In this section, WP leaders will be encouraged to write articles about their activities for publication on the website.
- “Public files” – Branding identity (files with logo, brand book) , public deliverables, newsletter, and papers/articles produced in the project
- “Clustering” – identification and link to similar projects
- “Contacts” – contacts of the WP Leader and executive board representative; project social media contacts

Figure 13 - E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators site graphic project

The information available on the website will be updated whenever necessary.

Social media channels

The project's social media channels are aimed at internal and external audiences and intend to engage the public and to inform about the project and its activities. Like the website, the social media allow the project to be visible to a wider audience. This media also benefit from the interaction with the audience and allows the project members to highlight ongoing activities.

The project social media will be activated soon after the project website is online. The social media more relevant to the project are: LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook and Youtube. The posts will contain announcements, information on results and events and will also tag the beneficiaries social accounts, enhancing the visibility of the information shared.

Social media activities will be planned and scheduled according to the needs of each WP. Whenever there is an event or face-to-face meeting, the designated team member responsible for communication at the host institution will be responsible for ensuring publications on the project's social media.

The use of #entrenovators will be mandatory. Other hashtags are recommended where relevant: #EuropeanUniversities, #Research, #HorizonEU, #EUFunded, #EUDRESalliance, #OpenScience #OpenAccess, #OpenEducation, #OpenEducationResources, #OpenInnovation, #OpenResearchEurope.

Print materials

In addition to the templates that support the digital presence of the project's identity, other graphic materials will ensure the project's physical presence at events and at in-person meetings, participation in conferences and scientific fairs, strengthening its visibility and notoriety. Some of these materials will be a roll-up, used in every in-person meeting or activity, an identifications card (Figure 14), and a brochure. The brochure will have a digital version, available on the website, and a printed version be used on every in-person occasion where it is useful to pass on general information about the project in a structured way.

Figure 14 - Print material examples

Press releases

Press releases (Figure 15) will be sent to the press whenever the project has an event, achievement or information relevant to the civil society. The press release is prepared by IPS-WP1 and then shared among all beneficiaries, for dissemination in the 6 regions involved. In order to reinforce the project's identity and notoriety, a template will be used respecting the Project's graphic identity. The main targets of this channel are external stakeholders and the general public. All press releases will be found on the website.

Figure 15 - Press releases template

Beneficiary channels

With the use of each institution's own channels (websites, social media, emails and others), it is intended to expand and increase the visibility and notoriety of the project locally and direct the information to the public of the 6 beneficiaries involved.

In order to promote and facilitate the involvement of all project beneficiaries in CDE activities, we have defined one team member per beneficiary, responsible for communication at their institution. This team members will make the link between the coordination of WP1, at IPS, and their institutions (and their marketing/communication' offices), dynamizing the dissemination of news and information about the project and its results in the institution channels.

Vídeo series

We will produce 9 short videos (3 per project year) on the projects' activities and results. These videos will be produced with the technical WP teams (WP2-6) and published online on project's webpage and social media to disseminate the project goals, activities and results.

Conference

This open event aims to bring together all people involved in the project (including industry, SMEs, citizens, civil society, and other organizations), and also policymakers, national science ministers, EU representatives linked to both the EEA and ERA, and representatives of the organizations and groups we are working with (e.g. EURASHE, EUA, FOREU2, etc.). The Conference is planned to happen in the final stage of the project. It will be an event to discuss the results of the project and the challenges to the future of E³UDRES² and other alliances. The main targets of this channel are the communities of the beneficiary institutions, external stakeholders and the general public. The main objectives are to summarize the main results achieved throughout this project.

European Researchers' Night

Each consortium partner will participate in the European Researchers' Night event. The participation in Science events like European Researchers' Night, aims to increase the awareness about the project and share our goals and achievements with the general public, high school students and children.

In addition to the activities described, as mentioned in the Proposal, whenever there is a need to create involvement with researchers, teachers and students, stakeholders or society, other forms of engagement will be explored, such as:

- Workshops
- Ideas competitions
- Online meetings and interactive sessions at wonder.me platform
- The I-Living Labs for Junior Ent-r-e-novators (T5.4) and Engagement Ambassadors (T5.5)

3.2 Channels by target dimensions

Given the different dynamics and needs of the communication within and about the Project, the Communication channels, listed in Figure 16, have different importance for the 1st and 2nd dimensions. Channels like EMDESK, meeting agendas/minutes, and sensitive deliverables are exclusive for the in-project communications. Channels like meetings, project templates, and emails, will have greater impact and importance in the communication within the project, but they will also have their role in the communication with external audiences such as stakeholders, relevant partners, and the press.

Figure 16 - Project channels by dimensions

On the other hand, logo and public deliverables sharing, have equal relevance for the two CDE dimensions of E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators. It is important that everyone includes the project's logo in their communication, increasing its notoriety. The sharing of deliverables is fundamental both in the in-project, sharing the results by all the teams' members, and externally for the success of the Dissemination and Exploitation objectives.

The press releases, the presence of the project on the channels of the beneficiary institutions, the series of videos, the conference, and the participation in the European Researchers' Night, are channels focused on the 2nd dimension of the CDE activities and on its impact on the public, as well as inside and outside the community of institutions. Finally, online presence activities such as the website and social networks, although they can contribute to strengthening the sharing of information between project team members, these channels, given their potential coverage, are essential for external audiences.

3.3 Channels activation calendar

Most of the previously described channels will be activated over the first six months of the project, as illustrated in Figure 17. The two exceptions are the Conference, planned for the final phase of the project, and the participation in the European Researchers' Night, which will take place, predictably, every September. CDE in-project activities were activated in the pre-start phase of the project, using email, and holding

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preparatory meetings between WP1 and all beneficiaries. In the 1st month, the first press release was published, promoting the project within the beneficiary institutions and the E³UDRES² alliance. In month 2 the graphic identity of the project was defined, and in month 3 the main templates were shared with the project team. It is intended that in month 5 the website will be available online and that in the following month the social media will also start to operate, in line with the website.

Figure 17 - Channels activation calendar

4. Internal and external target dimensions

To achieve the Communication goals, the CDE's efforts in the Project's internal and external dimensions will depend on the selection of the most appropriate channels and tools to reach the audiences and objectives of each dimension.

4.1 1st Target Dimension | Internal (within the project)

Figure 18 - 1st Dimension channels, targets, and goals

Concerning the internal project communication, the primary goal is to inform and support the project's operation and the activities among its members and WPs, ensuring compliance with objectives, conflict resolution, and the overcoming of the existing risks. The target is everyone involved in the project and the main goals are to inform and engage, sharing information, knowledge, skills and data, and support the WPs and WP members' work.

Figure 19 - Main project communication flow

Internal project communication is also a management tool. Figure 19 illustrates that the main project communication flow is supported by periodic meetings between the members of each WP and, monthly, between the leaders of all work packages. These meetings make it possible to periodically review the situation of the teams' activities and tasks, identify possible synergies, potential obstacles and adversities, and jointly seek timely solutions.

The respective minutes and meeting agendas are placed on EMDESK by the leaders of each WP and shared with the entire team. The sharing of these files with all team members not only allows a transversal sharing of information between teams, but also enhances a close articulation of their work.

4.2 2nd Target Dimension | External (about the project)

	COMMUNICATION	DISSEMINATION	EXPLOITATION
main message	Project and it's results	Project results	Project results and potential
goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raise awareness of the project objectives Raise awareness of the new European policies for Science and educations Inform the expected impacts to the region Engage targets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inform about project results to the scientific community Inform the expected impacts to the region 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inform about project results to the scientific community and production Inform the expected impacts to the region Engage Share knowledge, skills, data
targets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partners communities Regional Stakeholders Local Citizens Pre-college, undergraduate and graduate students Media 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific community Industrial partners Citizens and civil society Policy and decision makers Other European University Alliances and HEIs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Audiences including project partners that make concrete USE of the results Scientific community Industrial partners Other European Universities Alliances and HEIs Sectors of interest Civil society ...
channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project/partners social media Project/partner websites Project/partner newsletters Press releases Open events ... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project/partners website and social media Scientific magazines Databases and Repositories Open reports, deliverables and publications Conferences and meetings ... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Surveys Workshops Project/partners website and social media Ideas competitions Conferences and meetings The I-Living Labs for Junior Ent-r-e-novators (T5.4) and Engagement Ambassadors (T5.5) ...

Figure 20 - 2nd Dimension channels, targets, and goals

4.2.1 Communication goals, targets, channels, and messages

As mentioned before, the external communication will focus on promoting the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators actions and results. The main message for these targets will focus on the project: it is essential to present the project, explain it and make its goals clear to everyone. The main goals of Communication are to raise awareness of the project objectives, the new European policies for Science and educations, to inform the expected impacts to the region, and to engage targets.

The communication in the 2nd dimension should consider a multiple and wide audience, that includes each partner community, the project regional stakeholders, the 6 countries local citizens, pre-university, undergraduate and graduate students, and the press.

In this dimension, for the Communication to achieve these targets, the project will explore three sets of channels: those of the institutions, those of the project, and those of the mass media (i.e. through press releases and the holding of events).

4.2.2 Dissemination goals, targets, channels, and messages

The concerns of the project's Dissemination are to make the results public, so, later on, we will have to inform about the project results and the expected impacts on the region. Dissemination targets are all the audiences interested in the potential use of the results: Scientific community, Industrial partners, Citizens and civil society, for example. The message of the Dissemination effort will be centered on the project results.

Taking into account what was previously identified in the "Proposal template Part B: technical description", the main goals of the project E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators' dissemination activities are:

- To raise the interest of our students, researchers and professors in this project, making them want to know more and/or get more involved in the education, research and innovation activities of our European University;
- To attract research partners from other national and international (within and outside Europe) HEIs and applied research institutes;
- To create links and synergies with scientific and innovation networks and agencies;
- To attract regional SMEs, organizations and citizens to actively participate in our I-Living Labs and open innovation activities;
- To develop synergies and facilitate further efforts to attract funding to our research and innovation activities – covering all technological readiness levels (TRLs) from basic (but applied) research to close-to-market activities;
- To advocate for most-needed legal/regulatory changes among policymakers from both the Member States and the European Union.

Considering the Dissemination goals and targets, in addition to the project's and partners' websites and social media, for dissemination activities we must consider channels like Scientific magazines, Databases, Open reports, deliverables, and publications.

4.2.3 Exploitation goals, targets, channels, and messages

The Exploitation strategy will focus on the project results and potential, so, the Exploitation efforts will occur mainly in a final stage of the project. They will be centered on making concrete use of the results, and, for that to happen, the Exploitation goals must inform about project results, inform about the expected impacts on the region and engage. The Exploitation efforts will target all the audiences that can make concrete use of the results or that could be interested in it.

To achieve the Exploitation goals and targets, and increase the visibility of the project, we will use tools like surveys, workshops, conferences and meetings and also the channels provided for the European Union, like horizon magazine and cordis.

Associations and science and education policymakers at national and EU level and HEIs and European University Alliances are very important target groups for our Dissemination and Exploitation goals. Our efforts to reach these targets will go through activities previously described in the “Proposal template Part B: technical description”, that included the following actions:

- Attending to webinars from the European Universities Association (EUA), European Association of Institutions in Higher Education (EURASHE), All European Academies (ALLEA)
- Meetings with FOREU2 (subgroups) and the European Commission
- Participation in WP activities like Working Groups and Focus Groups
- Engagement and advocacy actions with national governments, and science ministers and agencies (usually led by our rectors and presidents)

4.2.4 Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation calendarization

Most of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation activities will share the same channels but, considering they have different goals and messages, their activities will be developed in different phases throughout the project.

Figure 21 - Calendarization by dimensions

Project No 101071317

Figure 21 illustrates the distribution of project CDE efforts considering the different dimensions and areas of activity. In-project communication and external communication activities were activated before the beginning of the project, with project preparatory meetings and with KoM's preparatory activities. The Communication activities will continue during the 36 months of the project. From the middle of the project, after the completion of some deliverables, dissemination activities will begin. Finally, the Exploitation activities will take place in the final months of the last year, when it will already be possible to create synergies for the use of the project results.

5. Responsibilities and Control

In the management of CDE activities, the responsibilities will be shared between the project coordinator, the WP leaders, and the communication link (responsible for communication in each institution). Responsibilities will be shared as follows:

Project Coordinator (WP1 Leader)	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interface between the Consortium and the European Commission. Promote an effective communication and collaboration between partners, including timely discussion of any challenges or unexpected changes Management the communication and documentation on the virtual platform (EMDESK) Team management in MS Teams Ensure the creation of the logo, brand book, templates, and printed materials Ensure the creation of the project's social media and website Management and updating of content on the projects' social media and website Prepare press releases Manage the preparation of face-to-face events Manage the preparation of the conference Ensuring the recording of evidence and the control of the methods of CDE activities Ensure the writing and delivery of the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan Ensure the writing and delivery of the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication 15 months report Ensure the writing and delivery of the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication final report 	
WP 2 to 6 Leaders	Communication link in each institution
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inform WP1 leader of all the relevant dissemination activities related with their WP tasks and activities Share meeting agendas and minutes Update information about WP task in EMDESK Collaborate in the preparation of face-to-face events Collaborate in the preparation of the final conference 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interface with their institution to ensure the dissemination of all relevant news, press releases and activity about the project in the channels of the institution Provide information about local project events Publish on the projects' social media information about local in site events Collaborate in the preparation of face-to-face events Collaborate in the registration of evidence and the control of the ethics of CDE activities Collaborate in the preparation of the final conference

Table 1 presents a summary of the project channels, target groups, frequency of the channels activities and control metrics. The monitoring of Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation activities will be carried out by IPS, within the scope of the Project Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan.

A periodic record of CDE activities will be kept. IPS-WP1 will record all project and dissemination channels within and through IPS's communication office. The team member that was defined at each institution to be the communication link, will also be responsible for recording their institution's CDE activities evidences. From

month 6 onwards, when most channels will be already activated, an update will be made every six months. This data will allow us to monitor the metrics defined for each project channel.

Table 1 -control metrics, frequency, and target groups of the channel's activities

Channels	Target Group		Beginning	Frequency	Control metrics
EMDESK	1 st dimension	Project Team	month 1	Throughout the whole project duration	# of regular users (54) Feedback from users (30)
Meetings		Project Team	month 1	Throughout the whole project duration	# of meeting per year
Meeting agendas/minutes		Project Team	month 1	Throughout the whole project duration	1 per WP meeting
Logo and Brand Book	1 st dimension 2 nd dimension	Project Team Project consortium External stakeholders General public	month 2	Throughout the whole project duration	Existing files
Project document and presentation templates		Project Team Project consortium External stakeholders General public	month 3	Throughout the whole project duration	Existing files
Emails		Project Team Project consortium External stakeholders	month 1	Throughout the whole project duration	
Sensitive Deliverables	1 st dimension n	Project Team	month 2	As defined in the Grant Agreement	As defined in the Grant Agreement
Public deliverables	1 st dimension 2 nd dimension	Project Team Project consortium External stakeholders General public	month 6	As defined in the Grant Agreement	As defined in the Grant Agreement
Project website	2 nd dimension	Project Team Project consortium External stakeholders General public	month 5	Throughout the whole project duration	# of visitors per month (avg 20)
Project social media		Project Team Project consortium External stakeholders General public	month 5	Throughout the whole project duration	# of visitors per month (avg 20) # of likes/month (avg 10)
Print materials	1 st dimension 2 nd dimension	Project Team Project consortium	month 6	Throughout the whole project duration	Existing files
Press releases	2 nd dimension	External stakeholders General public	month 1	Six per project year, Throughout the whole project duration	# of press releases per partner and per year (in total 18) Media cover (date, country, media name and type, key message(s))

Channels	Target Group		Beginning	Frequency	Control metrics
Beneficiaries' channels		Project consortium	month 1	Throughout the whole project duration	Institutions website- Number of web pages with information
E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators video series		Project consortium Stakeholders General public	month 12	At least once per project year	# of videos produced/year (3) # of videos published/year (3) # of visualisations per video and per year (100)
Conference		Project consortium Stakeholders General public	month 36	Once at the end of the project	Number and type of: - participants from the E³UDRES² (100) alliance - stakeholders (30) - citizens (20) Total = 150
Participation in the European Researchers' Night		General public High school students Children	Set 2023	Once per project year	# of partners participating/year (6)

ANNEX I | Brand Manual

Graphics standards manual

December 2022

This document is intended to be a practical guide to the project visual identity **EUDRES Ent-r-e-novators**.

It provides detailed information to the logo's use, graphic specifications, and examples on how to apply the project visual identity.

The identity was designed and thought out as a whole – that is why the combination of its elements results in a graphically coherent construction.

To ensure coherence and uniformity, the following guidelines must be respected.

To clarify any doubt resulting from the application of the usage rules presented here, please contact us.

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01. Logo

Logo

The logo was designed to graphically convey the values of the brand/project. As a brand that values the people involved in the project (entrepreneurs, researchers, educators and innovators), we felt the need to humanize the letter "e", with a loose and organic feel.

The result represents a happy "e", that illustrates the feeling of satisfaction/achievement/discovery, reminding us of a lit lightbulb (a great idea).

Main logo

Main logo

Alternative logo

Symbol

Elements

The logo consists of a symbol, typography and tagline.

The use of the symbol without the typography is allowed, but not the other way around. This provides greater flexibility while applying the brand to the various communication supports.

To ensure proper reading throughout the various formats, the logo features a main version plus an alternative version, for maximum versatility.

Main logo

Protection Area

For better visibility, it's essential that the logo has a protective area around it.

This is defined by the height of the letter "e", which outlines the brand's protective area in relation to another graphic object.

Main logo

Main logo

Alternative logo

Symbol

Minimum Dimensions

The reference used to represent the brand in reduced dimensions is the reading of the tagline.

When the tagline is lost, a version composed by the symbol and lettering may be used.

The symbol can be used individually, also respecting the minimum safety dimensions.

35 mm

50 mm

7 mm

Unsuitable Applications

When creating a brand, it is essential to maintain a coherent and concise approach in all its use. Breaking with graphic standards is disfiguring the brand and implies a poor representation of it.

This provides little professional accuracy to clients and partners.

To prevent this, there are some examples of applications that are not allowed when using the brand.

02.

EU Logo

EU Logo

EUDRES Ent-r-e-novators is a project financed by the European Union, so the communication must have the appropriate representation.

On the various communication pieces associated with the project, whenever the two logos appear simultaneously, the rules mentioned in this manual must be taken into account to ensure consistency in the representation of the brand.

The distance between the two logos respects the measure defined for the protective area, which is the height of the "e".

Whenever the EU logo appears in any piece of communication, it must be accompanied by the following text (represented in black in Arial font):

Project No 101071317

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency [REA]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

**Funded by
the European Union**

Project No 101071317

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency [REA]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

X		X		X
	<p>Funded by the European Union</p>			
X		X		X

Main logo

**Funded by
the European Union**

**Funded by
the European Union**

X		X		X
	<p>Funded by the European Union</p>			
X		X		X

Alternative logo

**Funded by
the European Union**

**Funded by
the European Union**

03. Colours

Colours

Colours are extremely important for brand identity, to assert itself in the market.

In this sense, cheerful and vivid colours were selected, in order to guarantee greater contrast and prominence.

The main colours present in the logo (Blue, Orange, Yellow and Green) are the basis of all brand communication.

In order to complement and enrich the graphic communication, complementary colours were also defined (Purple, Light Blue, Gray and Black).

For good use of colour, there must be a balance between colour, shape and background. When the colours previously defined are not used, colours or textures that conflict with the logo must be avoided.

Backgrounds

The application of rules to the background help maintain the chromatic integrity of the brand, ensuring the maximum contrast possible.

When applied on a coloured background (dark or light) or an image, the logo version that guarantees the highest possible contrast must be used. As an example, what follows are logo applications on colour and/or image backgrounds.

If the backgrounds used have colours other than those defined for the brand, colour tones that conflict with the logo should be avoided.

The brand colours were defined to work with each other, in order to create interesting chromatic dynamics. The symbol can be used in any colour that makes sense in the piece, however, the logo must respect the predefined colours of the brand, or, if not possible, the white version should be used instead.

The background can be composed of an image, but care should be taken to insure proper legibility and visibility.

04.

Typography

Logo's typography

Along with the project visual identity's elements, the use of typography is very important to the coherent representation.

The typography used in the logo's construction is 'Now', however it should not be used in communication and dissemination materials.

The "e" was specifically drawn to be the symbol of the brand

E³UDRES²

Font: Now Regular

**ent.r.e.
novators**

Font: Now Bold

ENTREPRENEURS + RESEARCHERS
EDUCATORS + INNOVATORS

Font: Now Regular

Main logo

Communication's material typography

Typography is essential for a coherent brand representation. The font used in brand communication is different from the one used in the design of the logo.

For titles, subtitles, highlights, texts, and institutional communication, the 'Volte' type family was chosen, which, with its variants (from Light to Bold) guarantees contrast and dynamics.

For internal documents, such as Word and/or PowerPoint, or in situations where it is not possible to use the predefined typography, the 'Arial' type family must be used (available on MAC and Windows systems).

Volte
Abc123&*

Font: Volte

Light *Italic*

Regular *Italic*

Medium *Italic*

Semibold *Italic*

Bold *Italic*

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

!"#\$%&/[()]=?*+-:;_~^@€'<>

1234567890

05. Templates

Covers

Index

Title and text

Tables

Back cover

Cover

Text + Image

Image

Topics + Image

Home chapter

Quote

Highlights

Contacts

Press Releases Examples

Horizontal 1/2

Full page

Vertical 1/2

Social media Profile

Facebook

Youtube

Linkedin

Twitter

Social media

Teams/Zoom background

06. Applications

Applications

In this document there are some examples of different uses for the logo. There are various types of applications, but the standard rules must be respected.

When in doubt about an application, please contact the responsible entity.

E³UDRES²
**ent.r.e.
novators**
ENTREPRENEURS + RESEARCHERS
EDUCATORS + INNOVATORS

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